

Circle packing inside a regular dodecagon: supplemental material

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular dodecagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular dodecagon that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 400$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular dodecagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 400$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [?] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceed by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular dodecagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.49133380994	0.505605644621	41	0.135307362001	0.786059333226
3	0.456625858814	0.655044609005	42	0.133407914534	0.782782483545
4	0.408248290464	0.698131700798	43	0.132361398066	0.788896020007
5	0.360457215913	0.680308771122	44	0.131244741439	0.793679417173
6	0.329459311299	0.681998533586	45	0.12955245631	0.790919776506
7	0.329459311299	0.79566495585	46	0.128134098346	0.790889635214
8	0.294687461094	0.727514944777	47	0.126888271657	0.792445565991
9	0.270902167318	0.691665456614	48	0.125894723452	0.796681828927
10	0.256656322814	0.689814872232	49	0.12500357728	0.801806515746
11	0.248926770057	0.713780223768	50	0.12346462652	0.798148526714
12	0.243095766159	0.742616602118	51	0.122315591989	0.799028807399
13	0.230908167326	0.725856146978	52	0.121434497325	0.80300106342
14	0.22599952768	0.748810139846	53	0.12087418712	0.810908066369
15	0.216453515072	0.735951445752	54	0.120772076915	0.824812905656
16	0.211918467266	0.752464835354	55	0.120740744368	0.839651378613
17	0.205484897731	0.751687548815	56	0.117768162735	0.81334058657
18	0.204124145232	0.785398163397	57	0.116885160624	0.815496740682
19	0.204124145232	0.829031394697	58	0.115785708038	0.814266416194
20	0.190550724215	0.760466033783	59	0.114770727582	0.813847248035
21	0.186129703363	0.761867211308	60	0.11418266671	0.819181680673
22	0.17963846595	0.74344693299	61	0.114120301269	0.83192518501
23	0.176340572223	0.74896400386	62	0.111608528486	0.808751449064
24	0.173878839335	0.759859547709	63	0.110305601402	0.802720401736
25	0.170362625375	0.75983146677	64	0.109513038363	0.803785650289
26	0.167677684105	0.765512876126	65	0.108776681372	0.80540363343
27	0.16620367923	0.78104067042	66	0.10796610927	0.805651937469
28	0.162997380513	0.779018729658	67	0.107329266937	0.808238896284
29	0.159263342623	0.770297110594	68	0.106808794524	0.812365661714
30	0.15849952794	0.78923405925	69	0.106521495686	0.819883639566
31	0.155891230621	0.788921301764	70	0.105176867124	0.810899661067
32	0.151891844499	0.773121068136	71	0.10435472163	0.809675828847
33	0.15092261919	0.787138627136	72	0.103732356789	0.811315185261
34	0.148120361074	0.781154716183	73	0.103243124303	0.814842654945
35	0.1464020722	0.785581251284	74	0.102252942603	0.810236805531
36	0.145105724217	0.793780103525	75	0.101369934662	0.807064444067
37	0.144948974278	0.81406790896	76	0.100771111569	0.808191555819
38	0.140383736593	0.784234258817	77	0.100259334768	0.810529788345
39	0.138883550489	0.787761670741	78	0.0995512457243	0.809499562663
40	0.137850626782	0.795987228334	79	0.0992348759033	0.814674965932

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular dodecagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0983730909645	0.810720658994	121	0.0807070206234	0.825347079199
81	0.097947948445	0.813774964484	122	0.080429989525	0.82646501254
82	0.0976736930376	0.819214607637	123	0.0800367109123	0.825110655496
83	0.0972156611556	0.821446301528	124	0.079637898595	0.823549839136
84	0.0967983561048	0.82422136489	125	0.0792850891109	0.822851884826
85	0.0966038879193	0.83068573857	126	0.0792191577998	0.828055803058
86	0.0952284587174	0.816696284475	127	0.0791992255271	0.834207727267
87	0.0946134115693	0.815555039547	128	0.0784904326264	0.825794589911
88	0.0942445928032	0.818510348897	129	0.0781627089863	0.82531081086
89	0.093621616665	0.816903764098	130	0.0778288946902	0.824619680914
90	0.0929981370737	0.815116388894	131	0.0774934807415	0.823816052815
91	0.0929136368176	0.8226761924	132	0.0772030784724	0.823894844961
92	0.092010514296	0.815626563902	133	0.0770853838899	0.827607348227
93	0.0914409079358	0.814315358141	134	0.0767416581391	0.826410399469
94	0.0909336064838	0.813964198436	135	0.0765071301216	0.827496583071
95	0.0904135530087	0.813241056001	136	0.076325270964	0.82966780143
96	0.0899798096399	0.813935500643	137	0.0759250094323	0.827025487979
97	0.0896295016247	0.816022841564	138	0.0756770728229	0.82763024833
98	0.0891482804304	0.815606418323	139	0.0754363552455	0.828332711425
99	0.0887810411939	0.817154695411	140	0.0752310209164	0.829756311411
100	0.088516948753	0.820505483978	141	0.0751095459035	0.832986577366
101	0.0881617527659	0.822073073862	142	0.0749842619976	0.836098039862
102	0.0879350785379	0.825948752098	143	0.0745243959305	0.831690200516
103	0.0871505729056	0.819230920147	144	0.0742655019472	0.831697414707
104	0.0867454792451	0.819512644326	145	0.074123061948	0.83426365302
105	0.0863734809616	0.82031142859	146	0.0740130981074	0.837526661562
106	0.0860430493236	0.821799872572	147	0.0738227056976	0.83893028002
107	0.0855365971733	0.819815894061	148	0.0736680960332	0.841103082342
108	0.0850543054457	0.818172688938	149	0.0736179223911	0.845633150933
109	0.0847811233477	0.82045251237	150	0.0736086515573	0.85109414116
110	0.0843761349681	0.820088191547	151	0.072968290389	0.841925972815
111	0.0839932184057	0.820049450682	152	0.072725113928	0.841862232017
112	0.0837672777931	0.8229916809	153	0.0724739819139	0.841558469921
113	0.0834497327303	0.824056447336	154	0.0721443773232	0.839371690304
114	0.0832000197853	0.826381009589	155	0.0718646675547	0.838283963072
115	0.0829158042499	0.82794424833	156	0.0715127279191	0.835448928146
116	0.0826541592055	0.829881402095	157	0.0711975910525	0.833410311878
117	0.0824145846097	0.832190258603	158	0.0708894300344	0.831474001048
118	0.082335195725	0.837686795604	159	0.0707705506805	0.833932486025
119	0.0815274835312	0.828292357304	160	0.070487420351	0.832476215728
120	0.081081293558	0.82613534174	161	0.0701475099379	0.829619616622

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular dodecahedron for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0699780805254	0.830744900471	182	0.0663246147291	0.838396540816
163	0.0697843843242	0.831252041509	183	0.0661440785411	0.838420037431
164	0.0695242308199	0.83012759627	184	0.0659938365782	0.839176270863
165	0.0694498124444	0.833402342136	185	0.0657351728589	0.837135896595
166	0.069246629358	0.833554466896	186	0.0656354479827	0.839109174959
167	0.069212694324	0.837754175001	187	0.0654201046828	0.838093927565
168	0.0689973429071	0.837534358665	188	0.0653129463891	0.839817691734
169	0.0688210195803	0.838219051245	189	0.0651047669176	0.838911212439
170	0.0685773729087	0.837219292122	190	0.0650383312427	0.841629594036
171	0.0683186198491	0.835801020258	191	0.064910630074	0.842740052155
172	0.068160732783	0.836807504854	192	0.0647689859878	0.843459127692
173	0.0680443236576	0.838800198232	193	0.0646574100377	0.844933511721
174	0.0680123561528	0.842856241146	194	0.0645939965665	0.84764627937
175	0.0676608753629	0.838961228639	195	0.064528300728	0.850283372942
176	0.0673427048177	0.83583854986	196	0.0644974265177	0.85382617041
177	0.0671761614927	0.836435106972	197	0.064418184941	0.856074994891
178	0.0669993997189	0.836739832095	198	0.0643974895424	0.859867793612
179	0.0668469580169	0.837615965052	199	0.0643951125258	0.864146762576
180	0.0666425860119	0.837152937397	200	0.063727477541	0.850573936492
181	0.0666519204105	0.842039620707			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular dodecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

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References

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